

INQUIRY- BASED LEARNING TOOLS IN ENHANCING THE PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILL OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS IN PROBABILITY AND STATISTICS

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ABSTRACT

Problem-solving skill is an integral skill necessary in taking Mathematics education. Integrating inquiry-based learning as a pedagogy in online distance learning should improve the problem-solving skills of the students. More so, the use of tools relative to inquiry-based learning during online distance learning is a big help to develop problem-solving skills of the students. To support, this study focused on the use of inquiry-based learning tools in terms of blogs and social networks and various publishing tools that aimed to determine its effectiveness in enhancing the problem-solving skill performance of the learners. The study used a quasi-experimental research design particularly the nonequivalent control group in conducting the study in which students answered pretest and posttest instruments and were participated by 60 Grade 10 students divided into two groups of the third grading period of the academic year 2020-2021. The result showed a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores performance of the student-respondents which implies that the use of inquiry-based learning tools helped students improve their problem-solving skills. This indicates a significant increase in their performance from not yet meeting expectations to fully meeting expectations in snapshots, concepts and applications, strategies and approaches, accuracy, and representations and communications. Thus, this study revealed that there is no significant difference in the posttest score performance of the two groups of respondents exposed to inquiry-based learning tools. The study suggests providing training and seminars relevant to the use of inquiry-based learning tools in Mathematics education not just for Grade 10 but also in all grade levels of junior high school and senior high school.

Keywords: Inquiry- Based Learning, Inquiry- Based Learning Tools, Problem- Solving Skill, Blogs and Social Networks, Various Publishing Tools